

Demonstrating a cost competitive, sustainable, scalable intensified microalgae bioprocess for the production of food-grade medium value, carbon negative ingredients exceeding market standards.

CleanAlgae2Value Key Messages

- 1. The CleanAlgae2Value project is a CBE JU Innovation Action funded project seeking to optimize the utilization of microalgae potential via a cascading approach to produce white-microalgae-derived medium-price ingredients, using solely CO₂ as a carbon source.**
- 2. The key project objective is to build and operate a replicable module to enhance relevant biorefineries' performance through a cost-competitive, sustainable, and scalable microalgae fractionation and valorisation process. Our "Micro-Algae Biorefinery Upgrade Module" – MABUM – will be built effectively and efficiently to unlock the production of ingredients including protein isolates, oils, natural pigments and starch.**
- 3. The project brings together 15 organizations from 9 European countries, collaborating with end-users and market-proven off-takers to manufacture carbon-negative ingredients that exceed market standards and to validate 15 prototypes, 13 for the food and 2 for the biopackaging markets.**
- 4. Holistic evaluations, including both empirical - surveys, workshops - and horizontal considerations - LCA, TEA, SSbD modelling, will allow for the assessment of market acceptance and environmental, economic and societal sustainability.** These estimations will further support and boost the project's DCE activities.
- 5. CleanAlgae2Value has received funding from the Circular Bio-based Joint Undertaking (JU) and its members under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101213354.** The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and **the Bio-based Industries Consortium.**
- 6. Disclaimer:** Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CBE JU. Neither the European Union nor the CBE JU can be held responsible for them.

